

Synthesis, characterization and antibacterial screening of new pyrazole and pyrazoline-5-one derivatives

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Abstract : A series of *N'*-(*p*-toluene sulphonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazoline-5-ones and *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted arylazo)pyrazoles have been synthesized and characterized by chemical analysis, IR and ¹H NMR spectral data. The compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli*.

Keywords : *N'*-(*p*-toluene sulphonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazoline-5-ones, *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted arylazo)pyrazoles, antibacterial activity, pyrazoles, pyrazoline-5-ones.

Introduction

Pyrazole and pyrazoline-5-ones represent important classes of heterocyclic compounds possessing a wide spectrum of biological activities¹⁻³. Besides, the traditional interest in pyrazoline derivatives which have been the basis of numerous dyes and drugs, a number of substituted pyrazoles are used as antidiabetic and antineoplastic agents^{4,5}. Also incorporation of hydrazono⁶ or azo^{7,8} group enhances the biological activity of heterocycles. In view of the biological activities displayed by arylazo pyrazoles⁹ and arylhydrazono pyrazoline-5-ones¹⁰, various pyrazole and pyrazoline-5-one derivatives have been synthesized.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The purity of the synthesized compounds was checked on silica gel-G TLC plates. FT-IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a JASCO FT-IR-5300 spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE spectrophotometer (400 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard. All the compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N analyses.

Antibacterial activity :

All the synthesized compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria, *S.*

aureus and Gram-negative bacteria, *E. coli* by agar diffusion method at a concentration 0.5 mg cm⁻³ using DMF as solvent. The zone of inhibition was measured in mm. Sulphamethaxazole was used as the control.

General methods for the synthesis :

Synthesis of 2-(substituted arylhydrazono)-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate (1a-j) :

The starting substituted primary amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (5 ml) and water (8 ml) was cooled to 0 °C. Cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was then added to it and the diazonium salt so formed was filtered into a cooled solution of sodium acetate (8 g) and ethyl acetoacetate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). The resulting solids were washed with water and crystallized from acetic acid to furnish **1a-j** (65–75%) : **1a**, m.p. 184 °C (Found : C, 62.15; H, 5.68; N, 11.47. C₁₂H₁₄N₂O₃ calcd. for : C, 61.53; H, 5.98; N, 11.96%); ν_{\max} 3450 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1520 cm⁻¹ (NH-N=C); δ 1.40 (3H, t, CH₂CH₃), 2.73 (3H, s, COCH₃), 4.30 (2H, q, CH₂CH₃), 7.28 (5H, s, ArH), 14.71 (1H, s, NH); **1b**, m.p. 65–66 °C; **1c**, 178–179 °C; **1d**, 70–72 °C; **1e**, 119–120 °C; **1f**, 45–46 °C; **1g**, 125–126 °C; **1h**, 90–91 °C; **1i**, 89 °C; **1j**, 117–118 °C.

Synthesis of N'-(p-toluene sulphonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazoline-5-ones (2a-j) :

A mixture of *p*-toluene sulphonyl hydrazide (0.001 mol) and 2-(substituted arylhydrazono)-ethyl-2,3-dioxobutyrate (1a-j; 0.001 mol) dissolved in methanol was refluxed for 6 h. The solids that separated on cooling were dried and crystallized from alcohol to yield 2a-j. The physical, analytical and spectral data of the compounds presented in Table 1 are consistent with the structures of the compounds. The steps involved in the synthesis of the compounds is presented in Scheme 1.

Synthesis of 2,3,4-pentanetrione-3-substituted arylhydrazones (3a-h) :

The starting substituted primary amine (0.01 mol) dissolved in a mixture of concentrated HCl (5 ml) and water (8 ml) was cooled to 0 °C. Cold aqueous solution of sodium nitrite was then added to it and the diazonium salt so formed was filtered into a cooled solution of sodium acetate (8 g) and acetylacetone (0.01 mol) in ethanol (25 ml). The resulting solids were washed with water and crystallized from acetic acid to furnish 3a-h (56–74%) : 3a, m.p. 92 °C (Found : C, 63.64; H, 5.57; N, 13.24.

Table 1. Physical, analytical and spectral data of *N'*-(*p*-toluene sulphonyl)-3-methyl-4-(substituted arylhydrazono)-2-pyrazoline-5-ones

Sl. no.	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield	Colour	Molecular formula	Analytical data	IR (ν, cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ, ppm)
1.	-H (2a)	198	52	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₃ S	Found : C, 54.76; H, 4.12; N, 15.14. Calcd. for : C, 55.30; H, 4.49; N, 15.73%	3439 (NH), 3065 (Ar-CH), 2916 (CH), 1657 (C=O cyclic), 1601 (C=N), 1527 (Heterocyclic, five membered ring), 1152 (SO ₂)	2.19 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.43 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.2–7.7 (9H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, s, NH)
2.	4'-CH ₃ (2b)	198–200	64	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	Found : C, 57.73; H, 4.28 ; N, 14.74. Calcd. for : C, 58.37; H, 4.86; N, 15.13%	3432 (NH), 3065 (Ar-CH), 2952 (CH), 1660 (C=O cyclic), 1587 (C=N), 1570 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1150 (SO ₂)	2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.39 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.41 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.0–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 8.10 (1H, s, NH)
3.	4'-OCH ₃ (2c)	178–179	60	Orange	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	Found : C, 55.15; H, 4.14 ; N, 13.90. Calcd. for : C, 55.95; H, 4.66; N, 14.50%	3200 (NH), 3070 (Ar-CH), 2935 (CH), 1676 (C=O cyclic), 1595 (C=N), 1548 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1157 (SO ₂)	2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 4.0 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃), 7.0–7.85 (8H, m, ArH), 7.98 (1H, s, NH)
4.	4'-Br (2d)	208–212	65	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SBr	Found : C, 56.15; H, 3.08; N, 12.23. Calcd. for : C, 56.89; H, 3.44; N, 12.87%	3410 (NH), 3076 (Ar-CH), 2960 (CH), 1685 (C=O cyclic), 1591 (C=N), 1547 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1176 (SO ₂)	2.34 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.1–7.85 (8H, m, ArH), 8.10 (1H, s, NH)

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

5.	4'-NO ₂ (2e)	100-102	58	Dark yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	Found : C, 50.16; H, 3.34; N, 17.04, Calcd. for : C, 50.87; H, 3.74; N, 17.40%	3400 (NH), 3095 (Ar-CH), 2935 (CH), 1697 (C=O cyclic), 1597 (C=N), 1541 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1165 (SO ₂)	2.19 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.41 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.1-8.2 (8H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, s, NH)
6.	2'-CH ₃ (2f)	120-124	61	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃ S	Found : C, 57.85; H, 4.38; N, 14.90. Calcd. for : C, 58.37; H, 4.86; N, 15.13%	3300 (NH), 3080 (Ar-CH), 2968 (CH), 1670 (C=O cyclic), 1605 (C=N), 1554 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1161 (SO ₂)	2.30 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.35 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.37 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.2-7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 7.85 (1H, s, NH)
7.	2'-OCH ₃ (2g)	168-170	68	Brown	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄ S	Found : C, 55.24; H, 4.18; N, 14.10. Calcd. for : C, 55.95; H, 4.66; N, 14.50%	3390 (NH), 3060 (Ar-CH), 2968 (CH), 1690 (C=O cyclic), 1602 (C=N), 1570 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1140 (SO ₂)	2.33 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.39 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 3.85 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃), 7.0-7.7 (8H, m, ArH), 7.95 (1H, s, NH)
8.	2'-Cl (2h)	108-114	62	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₃ SCl	Found : C, 51.35; H, 3.53; N, 13.96. Calcd. for : C, 52.24; H, 3.84; N, 14.34%	3390 (NH), 3085 (Ar-CH), 2968 (CH), 1680 (C=O cyclic), 1610 (C=N), 1580 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1162 (SO ₂)	2.32 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.42 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.25-7.78 (8H, m, ArH), 7.89 (1H, s, NH)
9.	2'-NO ₂ (2i)	222-224	53	Orange	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₅ S	Found : C, 55.08; H, 3.37; N, 16.94. Calcd. for : C, 50.87; H, 3.74; N, 17.40%	3410 (NH), 3076 (Ar-CH), 2960 (CH), 1685 (C=O cyclic), 1591 (C=N), 1547 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1176 (SO ₂)	2.34 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.40 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.1-7.85 (8H, m, ArH), 8.10 (1H, s, NH)
10.	4'-SO ₂ NH ₂ (2j)	240-241	61	Yellow	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₅ S ₂	Found : C, 54.28; H, 4.08; N, 16.53. Calcd. for : C, 56.96; H, 4.34; N, 17.07%	3385 (NH), 3060 (Ar-CH), 2935 (CH), 1670 (C=O cyclic), 1595 (C=N), 1543 (Heterocyclic five membered ring), 1165 (SO ₂)	2.35 (3H, s, CH ₃), 2.42 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 7.0-7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 7.92 (1H, s, NH), 3.2 (2H, s, NH)

- R = a : -H
 b : 4'-CH₃
 c : 4'-OCH₃
 d : 4'-Br
 e : 4'-NO₂
 f : 2'-CH₃
 g : 2'-OCH₃
 h : 2'-Cl
 i : 2'-NO₂
 j : 4'-SO₂NH₂

Scheme 1

C₁₁H₁₂N₂O₂ calcd. for : C, 64.70; H, 5.88; N, 13.72%;
 v_{max} 3380 (NH), 1678 (C=O), 1591 cm⁻¹ (NH-N=C);
 δ 2.41 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.53 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.26 (5H, s, ArH), 14.61 (1H, s, NH); **3b**, m.p. 98 °C; **3c**, 100–101 °C; **3d**, 139–140 °C; **3e**, 202 °C; **3f**, 233 °C; **3g**, 112 °C; **3h**, 120 °C.

Synthesis of N'-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted arylazo)pyrazoles (4a-h) :

A mixture of salicylhydrazide (0.001 mol) and 2,3,4-

pentanetrione-3-substituted arylhydrazone (**3a-h**; 0.001 mol) dissolved in acetic acid was refluxed for 6 h. The solids that separated on cooling were dried and crystallized from alcohol to yield **4a-h**. The physical, analytical and spectral data of the compounds presented in Table 2 are consistent with the structures of the compounds. The steps involved in the synthesis of the compounds is presented in Scheme 2.

- R = a : -H
 b : 4'-CH₃
 c : 4'-OCH₃
 d : 4'-Cl
 e : 4'-SO₂NH₂
 f : 4'-NO₂
 g : 2'-CH₃
 h : 2'-Cl

Scheme 2

Antibacterial activity :

Antibacterial activity of the compounds **2a-j** and **4a-h** was tested *in vitro* against Gram-positive bacteria, *S. aureus*

Note

Table 2. Physical, analytical and spectral data of *N'*-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)-3,5-dimethyl-4-(substituted arylazo)pyrazoles

Sl. no.	R	M.p. (°C)	Yield %	Colour	Molecular formula	Analytical data	IR (v, cm ⁻¹)	¹ H NMR (δ, ppm)
1.	-H (4a)	234–238	70	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂	Found : C, 66.86; H, 4.82; N, 17.26. Calcd. for : C, 67.50; H, 5.00; N, 17.50%	3288 (OH), 3074 (Ar-CH), 1604 (C=N), 1554 (C=C), 1506 (N=N)	2.5 (6H, s, CH ₃), 7.1–7.5 (9H, m, ArH).
2.	4'-CH ₃ (4b)	62–64	68	Brown	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	Found : C, 67.47; H, 5.06; N, 16.38. Calcd. for : C, 68.26; H, 5.38; N, 16.76%	3300 (OH), 3065 (Ar-CH), 1605 (C=N), 1555 (C=C), 1510 (N=N)	2.3 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 2.6 (6H, s, CH ₃), 7.1–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 14.8 (1H, s, OH)
3.	4'-OCH ₃ (4c)	76–78	54	Yellow	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₃	Found : C, 64.55; H, 4.94; N, 15.76. Calcd. for : C, 65.14; H, 5.14; N, 16.00%	3276 (OH), 3070 (Ar-CH), 1610 (C=N), 1540 (C=C), 1503 (N=N)	2.6 (6H, s, CH ₃), 3.9 (3H, s, Ar-OCH ₃), 6.9–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 14.7 (1H, s, OH)
4.	4'-Cl (4d)	148–150	52	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	Found : C, 60.16; H, 4.04; N, 15.35. Calcd. for : C, 60.93; H, 4.23; N, 15.79%	3271 (OH), 3068 (Ar-CH), 1603 (C=N), 1560 (C=C), 1510 (N=N)	2.5 (6H, s, CH ₃), 7.0–7.6 (8H, m, ArH), 14.6 (1H, s, OH)
5.	4'-SO ₂ NH ₂ (4e)	290–292	53	Brown	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₅ O ₄ S	Found : C, 53.45; H, 4.08; N, 17.26. Calcd. for : C, 54.13; H, 4.26; N, 17.54%	3285 (OH), 3084 (Ar-CH), 1602 (C=N), 1554 (C=C), 1520 (N=N)	2.5 (6H, s, CH ₃), 3.0 (2H, s, NH ₂), 7.0–7.5 (8H, m, ArH), 14.8 (1H, s, OH)
6.	4'-NO ₂ (4f)	104–106	55	Yellow	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₄	Found : C, 58.43; H, 3.87; N, 19.02. Calcd. for : C, 59.17; H, 4.10; N, 19.17%	3294 (OH), 3064 (Ar-CH), 1618 (C=N), 1560 (C=C), 1530 (N=N)	2.6 (6H, s, CH ₃), 6.9–7.9 (8H, m, ArH), 14.8 (1H, s, OH)
7.	2'-CH ₃ (4g)	100–102	68	Pale yellow	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂	Found : C, 67.64; H, 5.12; N, 16.29. Calcd. for : C, 68.26; H, 5.38; N, 16.76%	3280 (OH), 3056 (Ar-CH), 1630 (C=N), 1570 (C=C), 1528 (N=N)	2.5 (6H, s, CH ₃), 2.4 (3H, s, Ar-CH ₃), 6.9–7.8 (8H, m, ArH), 14.8 (1H, s, OH)
8.	2'-Cl (4h)	100–102	52	Dark Brown	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ Cl	Found : C, 60.12; H, 4.06; N, 15.48. Calcd. for : C, 60.93; H, 4.23; N, 15.79%	3317 (OH), 3069 (Ar-CH), 1620 (C=N), 1582 (C=C), 1526 (N=N)	2.6 (6H, s, CH ₃), 7.0–7.7 (8H, m, ArH), 14.8 (1H, s, OH)

and Gram-negative bacteria, *E. coli* by cup plate technique^{11,12} at a concentration of 0.5 mg cm⁻³. Sulphamethaxazole (zone of inhibition 17–19 mm against

the selected bacteria) was used as the control. Compounds **2d**, **2e** and **2j** exhibited maximum activity (zone of inhibition 6–8 mm) against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Compounds

2h and **2i** exhibited moderate activity (zone of inhibition 3–5 mm). Rest of the compounds **2a**, **2b**, **2c**, **2f**, **2g** were found to be inactive against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Compound **4e** exhibited moderate activity (zone of inhibition 5–6 mm) against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. **4d**, **4f**, **4h** exhibited feeble activity (zone of inhibition 1–2 mm). Rest of the compounds were found to be inactive.

References

1. H. A. Etman, E. G. Sadek and M. A. Metwally, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **67**, 213.
2. K. Klemm, E. Cängensceid and G. Luowing, Ger. Pat. 2 508 934/1975 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1976, **84**, 44041).
3. E. L. Anderson, J. E. Casey, L. G. Greene, J. L. Lafferty and H. E. Reiff, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, **7**, 259.
4. R. E. Harman, F. E. Dutton and H. D. Warren, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 627.
5. H. G. Garg and C. Prakash, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 175.
6. W. C. J. Ross and G. P. Warweek, *J. Chem. Soc., Chemother. Rep.*, 1961, **14**, 85.
7. R. H. Wiley and R. Clovenger, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1962, **5**, 1367.
8. E. Messarans, D. Maldi, S. Rossi and L. Degan, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, **14**, 635.
9. Rajeev Jain, P. Padmaja, T. Sandeep and K. S. Mahendra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **77**, 44.
10. M. Amir and A. Rajesh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 154.
11. A. L. Barry, "The Antimicrobial Susceptibility Test : Principles and Practices", 1976.
12. F. Cavangh, "Analytical Microbiology", Academic. New York, 1963.